

1 A Novel Microinjection-Based Protocol Approach to Evaluate Gap Junction

2 Dynamics in 3D Multicellular Spheroids

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5 Disclosure statement

6 *The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.*

7 Abstract

8 Background:

9 In-vitro studies have been the centerpiece of most drug and cellular mechanisms studies.

10 Numerous drugs influence various cellular functions, including intercellular communication and

11 signaling. However, the ability to quantify and visually assess these changes has been limited,

12 particularly in advanced in-vitro models such as organoids and spheroids.

13 Objective:

14 To overcome these limitations, we developed a novel microinjection protocol that enables precise

15 dye delivery into individual cells within intact spheroids. This approach allows real-time

16 visualization of gap junctions activity in live cells, providing a more refined and physiologically

17 relevant assessment of intercellular communication. To further enhance the tumor

18 microenvironment model, fibroblasts were incorporated into spheroid co-culture to simulate in-

19 vivo cellular interactions. This protocol enables the analysis of gap junction functionality by

20 measuring dye movement between cells based on the extent of its spread.

21 Methods:

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22 For this protocol, fibroblasts were co-cultured with colorectal cancer epithelial cells using
23 CelVivo, Clinostar reactor to generate spheroids exceeding 300 µm in diameter. Microinjection
24 was performed with an Eppendorf Microinjector, delivering a dye mixture of Texas Red and
25 Lucifer Yellow to evaluate gap junction activity.

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26 Conclusion:

27 In summary, this protocol presents a novel approach for assessing gap junction activity in 3D
28 spheroids, including co-culture models. It enables the examination of the critical role of gap
29 junctions within complex 3D systems in a unique and physiologically relevant manner.

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30 ~~In vitro studies have been the centerpiece of most drug and cellular mechanisms studies.~~
31 ~~However, 90% of drug that enter clinical studies will fail for a multitude of reasons including~~
32 ~~clinical efficacy and unmanageable toxicity. To overcome these challenges, sophisticated models,~~
33 ~~mimicking in vivo conditions, were made to help reproduce the efficacy in clinical studies. Three-~~
34 ~~dimensional (3D) spheroids using patient derived cells serve as physiologically relevant models~~
35 ~~that enhance cancer research by better replicating the tumor microenvironment. However,~~
36 ~~assessing cell communication functionality via gap junction in 3D model remains a challenge.~~
37 ~~Traditional methods often require disrupting spheroids or depend on dye diffusion through the~~
38 ~~surrounding media, limiting the accuracy of gap junction analysis.~~

39 ~~To overcome these limitations, we developed a novel microinjection technique that enables precise~~
40 ~~dye delivery into individual cells within intact spheroids. This approach allows for real time~~
41 ~~visualization of gap junction activity in live cells, offering a more refined and physiologically~~
42 ~~relevant assessment of intercellular communication. To further enhance the tumor~~
43 ~~microenvironment model, fibroblasts were incorporated into spheroid co-cultures, simulating in-~~
44 ~~vivo cellular interactions.~~

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45 ~~For this study, fibroblasts were co-cultured with colorectal cancer epithelial cells using a CelVivo~~
46 ~~Clinostar reactor to generate spheroids exceeding 300 µm in diameter. Microinjection was~~
47 ~~performed with an Eppendorf FemtoJet, delivering a dye mixture of Texas Red and Lucifer Yellow~~
48 ~~to evaluate gap junction activity.~~

49 ~~In summary, this study introduces a novel approach for assessing gap junction activity in 3D~~
50 ~~spheroids while examining the critical role of fibroblasts in modulating gap junction dynamics in~~
51 ~~colorectal cancer cells.~~

52 Key Words

53 3D Spheroid, Gap Junction, Microinjection, Cell-Cell Communication, Co-Culture,
54 ~~Colorectal~~Colorectal Cancer

55 Introduction:

56 Colorectal cancer continues to be the second most deadly cancer around the world for both men
57 and women with an incidence of close to 150,000 and around 50,000 deaths per year.^{1,2} Despite
58 ongoing research in drug development and treatment, significant gaps and fundamental knowledge
59 remain in the field of colorectal cancer. One key area involves cell-to cell communication,
60 specifically gap junction-mediated signaling, and how to effectively visualize and analyze the
61 impact of external factor chemicals treatments on this type of communication within 3D models.

62 ³⁻⁶

63 ~~One such area is cell to cell communication, particularly concerning gap junctions. Gap junctions'~~
64 ~~channels are composed of several proteins called connexins forming the key component for cell-~~
65 ~~to cell communication. To understand this further, it is essential to consider the molecular basis of~~
66 gap junctions, which are formed by channel structures composed of connexin proteins which are
67 key components that enable direct intercellular communication.

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68 ⁷⁻¹⁰ Six connexins form to make a unit called connexons that vary in structure and combination of
69 each other in different types of tissue and cells. ^{4,11,12} ~~Recent findings convey that the improper or~~
70 ~~abnormal expression of connexins to form these gap junctions will result in inadequate and~~
71 ~~disturbed communication between cells that results in abnormal growth or function. These~~
72 ~~connexins vary in type and composition across different tissues, contributing to their diverse~~
73 ~~physiological roles. Abnormal or dysregulated expressions of connexins can disrupt gap junction~~
74 ~~communication, ultimately contributing to altered cellular growth, differentiation, and tumor~~
75 ~~progression.~~ ^{7,9,10,13}

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76 ~~Previous studies examining connexon expression and alterations have largely relied on 2D~~
77 ~~monolayer cultures, which fail to accurately mimic in vivo conditions. As a result, there has been~~
78 ~~a growing emphasis on developing in vitro models that more closely reflect the physiological~~
79 ~~environment as in-vivo.~~ ¹⁴⁻¹⁶ ~~The variability between 2D and 3D cultures comes from the greater~~
80 ~~complexity of 3D systems and their enhanced ability to interact with both their environments and~~
81 ~~neighboring cells.~~ ¹⁶⁻¹⁸ ~~These interactions contribute to the resemblance of 3D cultures to in vivo~~
82 ~~conditions, particularly in gene expression, morphology, and signaling pathways.~~ ^{19,20} ~~These~~
83 ~~signaling pathways and gene expression have been illustrated to affect cell-cell communication in~~
84 ~~3D models, especially in E-cadherin and N-cadherin.~~

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85 ~~In addition to changes in E-cadherin and N-cadherin, gap junction-mediated communication also~~
86 ~~differs between 2D and 3D models. Significant variations in both expression and functional~~
87 ~~activity of gap junctions are seen, particularly when organoids are involved.~~ ^{15-17,21-26} ~~One such~~
88 ~~example is the expression of connexin 43 which regulates anti-apoptotic and proliferative signals~~
89 ~~while also influencing cancer cell motility which increases metastasis rate.~~ ^{10,24,27} ~~Studies have~~
90 ~~demonstrated connexin 43 expression in certain cancer cell types are drastically different between~~

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91 3D model and 2D models leading to differences in gap junction regulation.²⁴ These changes affect
92 how drugs act on both the cells and the culture system, influencing their potency or lethality.²⁸⁻³¹
93 This highlights the need for reliable model systems and diverse assay approaches to investigate
94 gap junction alterations and interactions.

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95 One example of these assays is the Scrape Loading/Dye Transfer assay, which utilizes a
96 small dye (less than 900 Da) that can pass between cells exclusively through intercellular pathways
97 such as gap junctions.³²⁻³⁴ The dye is introduced by mechanically scraping ~~the~~100% confluent
98 population of attached cells and permits dye entry. After extensive washing, dye is then transferred
99 through ~~each~~the adjacent cells using primary gap junctions. The transfer of dye can then be
100 measured using fluorescent microscopy overtime.³⁴ However, a major limitation of this protocol
101 is its incompatibility with 3D models, as the scraping step required for dye introduction disrupts
102 or damages the spheroids. The key challenge lies in delivering the dye without compromising the
103 structural integrity of the spheroids, making this assay ineffective for use in 3D systems.

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104 Additionally, parachute assay is another useful tool to measure functionality of gap
105 junctions.^{35,36} The central concept of this technique involves using dye-preloaded cells that, when
106 co-cultured with unlabeled cells, can transfer the dye through intercellular connections.³⁶ Dye
107 transfer begins once the pre-loaded cells adhere to the monolayer, enabling intercellular
108 interactions that facilitate dye spread.^{35,37} While this technique is well-suited for experiments
109 involving 2D monolayers or 2D co-cultures, it is not a feasible approach for most 3D models. A
110 major challenge lies in integrating the dye-loaded cells into spheroids though possible, the process
111 is inconsistent, and the integration occurs at random locations within the structure.^{25,38} For
112 instance, depending on the method used to generate the spheroid or organoid, the parachuted dye-
113 loaded cells may fail to integrate into the spheroid and instead become trapped in the extracellular

114 matrix between spheroids, rather than being incorporated into the spheroid itself.^{25,38} Similarly, in
115 methods that form 3D models without an extracellular matrix, such as those relying on
116 gravitational forces, dye-loaded cells introduced after spheroid formation may fail to fully
117 integrate.³⁹ Alternatively, if the dye-loaded cells are added during the early stages of spheroid or
118 organoid formation, the dye may become trapped within the spheroid core. This internal
119 localization, combined with dense cell layering, can obstruct fluorescence signals from escaping,
120 limiting the ability to visualize dye transfer.^{6,35,37-39} Therefore, this protocol cannot be reliably
121 used to assess gap junction functionality in 3D models.

122 Lastly, one of the more advanced methods for assessing gap junctions involves the use of
123 quantitative fluorescence resonance energy transfer, commonly known as FRET.^{40,41} This
124 technique is based on the interaction between donor and acceptor fluorophores when they are in
125 close proximity, energy transfer occurs, resulting in light emission that can be quantitatively
126 measured.^{41,42} When applying the FRET method to assess gap junctions, it is typically performed
127 on a limited number of cells. One group of cells is loaded with donor fluorophores, while the other
128 is loaded with acceptor-labeled molecules.⁴⁰⁻⁴³ If these molecules meet in an adjacent cell, a FRET
129 signal is generated, indicating that the molecules have passed through functional gap junctions.
130 There has been limited application of the FRET method in 3D models, and its use still faces notable
131 challenges. One key limitation is uneven distribution of donor and acceptor molecules, where
132 certain regions may receive neither label, resulting in an absence of detectable signal.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶

133 Therefore, there is currently no definitive technique to both visualize and functionally assess gap
134 junction activity to the best of our knowledge. This protocol aims to address this research gap by
135 utilizing microinjection in 3D models. The advantage of using the microinjection protocol over
136 other methods lies in its ability to precisely target a specific region of the spheroid while delivering

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137 a controlled dose of dye. Similarly, this technique ensures that the dye remains confined within the
138 cell, preventing external leakage, as it is delivered directly into the cell's interior. Once delivered,
139 the dye will transfer to neighboring cells through intercellular mechanisms. Thus, this protocol
140 will describe and emphasize the use of microinjection as a tool for analyzing gap junctions in 3D
141 models.

142 ~~The expression of connexin 43 regulates anti-apoptotic and proliferative signals while also~~
143 ~~influencing cancer cell motility increasing metastasis rate. Specifically, increased expression~~
144 ~~regulates Snail-1, which suppresses E-cadherin, leading to epithelial-mesenchymal transition in~~
145 ~~cells.~~

146 ~~While the impact of connexin 43 on cancer cell behavior is clear, the challenges in~~
147 ~~assessing these effects in a complex model reveal a critical gap in our current experimental~~
148 ~~capabilities. Since complex models exhibit similar environments to in-vivo experiments,~~
149 ~~especially in 3D spheroids, there is a substantial need to conduct vital experiments in these~~
150 ~~complex models. 3D models illustrate vastly different cell-to-cell mechanisms and cell-to-~~
151 ~~environmental interactions compared to 2D monolayer culture. One such example is displayed~~
152 ~~with the cellular pathway involved with AKT. In 3D applications, colorectal cancer cells show a~~
153 ~~decreased amount of AKT activity compared to their 2D counterpart.~~

154 ~~Since 3D models more accurately replicate tumor physiology, investigating gap junctions~~
155 ~~within these systems is crucial for understanding their true role in cancer progression. However,~~
156 ~~the inherent complexity of 3D models poses significant challenges in conducting these~~
157 ~~experiments. Most studies on gap junctions in 3D models focus on evaluating connexin~~
158 ~~expression or measuring molecule uptake. However, directly observing the uptake of molecules~~
159 ~~remains a gap in this area of research. Alternative methods have been developed to directly~~

160 observe molecule uptake through gap junctions; however, most of these techniques rely on 2D
161 monolayer cultures, which fail to replicate the in vivo like conditions necessary for accurate
162 analysis. Examples of these techniques include Parachute assay, scrape load dye transfer assay,
163 Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer FRET microscopy, or microinjection into individual
164 cells; however, to the best of our knowledge, neither of these methods has been implemented in
165 3D spheroid models. This paper will discuss the application of microinjection in co-culture
166 spheroids to assess gap junction functionality through dye measurement.

167 Materials

- 168 1. Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, Gibco, Cat no. 11966025) cell
169 culture medium: DMEM with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS)
- 170 2. RPMI 1640 (Gibco, Cat no. 31800) cell culture medium: RPMI with 10% fetal
171 bovine serum (FBS)
- 172 3. Incubator set to 37°C, humidity 95 %, CO₂ 5 %.
- 173 4. CelVivo Clinostar incubator (Invitro Technologies)
- 174 5. Nikon Ts2R-FI Inverted Microscope
- 175 6. Eppendorf™ FemtoJet™ 4i Microinjector
- 176 7. Eppendorf TransferMan 4r Micromanipulator
- 177 8. Eppendorf™ Femtotips™ Microinjection Capillary Tips (Eppendorf™, Cat no.
178 E5242957000)
- 179 9. Eppendorf™ Femtotips™ Microloader Tips for Femtojet Microinjector
180 (Eppendorf™, Cat no. 930001007)

- 181 10. Dye solutions: Lucifer Yellow (457.2 Da, green); Texas Red-dextran (10,000 Da,
182 red) did not. Both were 1 mM solutions mixed 1:1 in the Microloader Tips
- 183 11. Penicillin-Streptomycin (Gibco, Cat no. 15140122)
- 184 12. Caco-2 (ATCC® HTB-37)
- 185 13. T75 (EasYFlask, Thermofisher, Cat no. 156499)
- 186 14. Class II A2 Biological Safety Cabinet
- 187
- 188 15. Cell counter
- 189 16. Phosphate buffered saline, pH 7.4 (Gibco, Cat no. 10010023)
- 190 17. Trypsin-EDTA (0.5%), no phenol red
- 191 18. Petri Dishes with Clear Lid (Fisher Scientific, Cat no FB0875714)
- 192 19. Glass Bottom 35mm Cell Culture Dish

193 Methods

194 Establishment of 3D spheroids

- 195 1. Cell growth media for Caco2 with Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM). Add
196 10% Fetal bovine serum and 0.5% penicillin/streptomycin to DMEM media. Grow cells
197 to 80% confluency and prepare 3D CellVivo Culture system.
- 198 2. Prepare the Cellvivo culture by injecting 25 mL of sterile water into the hydration port of
199 the ClinoReactor using a 20-gauge ½-inch needle through the plastic seal, ensuring sterile
200 conditions inside a laminar airflow cabinet. Cover the hole created from the 20- gauge

201 needle with sterilized tape and place the ClinoReactor in a 4°C fridge overnight. After
202 equilibration, wash the front port three times with sterilized PBS and take reactor out of
203 the plastic cover.

204 3. Rinse the adherent cells in a T-75 flask three times with PBS. Treat the cells with 3 mL of
205 Trypsin-EDTA (0.5%), no phenol red, to detach them, then pellet the cells by
206 centrifugation. Resuspend the pellet in 5 mL of DMEM containing 10% FBS. Count the
207 cells and seed 5×10^4 cells into the ClinoReactor chamber. Fill the chamber to its
208 maximum capacity with approximately 5 mL of DMEM, ensuring no bubbles are
209 introduced.

210 4. Incubate the ClinoReactor in the Clinostar at 37°C with 5% CO₂ at a rotation speed of 13
211 rpm for one day. This speed keeps the cells suspended in the center of the reactor,
212 promoting spheroid formation. Gradually increase the rotation speed by 0.5 rpm per day
213 to maintain the spheroids in the center. After two weeks, the spheroids will reach an
214 optimal size of 300 microns for microinjections. Additionally, change the media as
215 needed by allowing the spheroids to settle at the bottom of the chamber. Carefully replace
216 the media, ensuring that approximately 200 µL remains to prevent spheroid loss during
217 pipetting.

218 Microinjection of spheroids

219 1. Remove the ClinoReactor from the Clinostar and place it in a sterile laminar flow hood.
220 Carefully open the front port and gently extract the spheroids using wide-bore pipette
221 tips. Transfer all spheroids into a 150 mm petri dish, allowing them to spread out. Select a
222 single spheroid and use a pipette to pass it through a 70 µm cell strainer to remove any

223 small or single cells, handling it carefully to avoid disruption. Place the spheroid in a
224 glass-bottom 35 mm cell culture dish and add 2 mL of DMEM, ensuring the spheroid is
225 positioned at the center of the small chamber within the dish.

226 2. Dip the micropipette into the dye solution of Luciferase Yellow and Texas Red while
227 ensuring the micropipette is not touching any surface or broken. Slowly fill the
228 micropipette with dye without introducing any air bubbles and mount the micropipette to
229 the micromanipulator and angle the micropipette at 33°C from the microscope stage.
230 Ensure the Eppendorf™ FemtoJet™ 4i Microinjector is one and at the lowest injection
231 pressure and compensation pressure. Carefully position the micropipette into the media
232 using the micromanipulator while observing under the microscope.

233 3. Once the micropipette is in the media without touching the surface or any spheroids
234 adjust the compensation pressure to allow consistent leakage of dye from the tip of the
235 micropipette. Increase the injection pressure by 25 psi, adjusting as needed based on the
236 cell type and spheroid thickness. Do not exceed 60 psi, as higher pressure may damage or
237 rupture the cells.

238 4. Carefully maneuver the spheroid to the edge of the 35 mm petri dish, positioning it
239 against the walls of the inner chamber using the micropipette. Be sure not to penetrate the
240 spheroid at this stage. Once the spheroid is positioned against the chamber wall, gently
241 insert the micropipette into the spheroid and inject the dye. The injection should take
242 between 0.5 to 1 second, ensuring the volume is small enough to avoid inducing
243 apoptosis. Make sure there is only one injection point and allow sufficient time before
244 fixing the spheroids to ensure proper time intervals. Once the time intervals are
245 completed proceed to fix and image the spheroid.

246 Fixing and Imaging of Spheroid

- 247 1. Transfer the spheroid to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf microcentrifuge tube and gently wash it
248 with PBS to remove any residual background dye.
- 249 2. Cover the Eppendorf tube with foil to protect the dye from light exposure.
- 250 3. Add 1 mL of 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS and incubate for 1 hour.
- 251 4. Wash the spheroids with PBS three times.
- 252 5. Transfer the spheroid to a 35 mm petri dish and prepare it for imaging. Use an excitation
253 wavelength of 485 nm and emission wavelength of 540 nm for Luciferase Yellow, and an
254 excitation wavelength of 580 nm and emission wavelength of 640 nm for Texas Red.
255 Adjust the exposure time and gain settings to capture the best image of the control,
256 maintaining these settings throughout the imaging process.

257 Discussion:

258 This protocol outlines a reliable workflow for generating 3D spheroids, including both
259 monocultures and epithelial–fibroblast co-cultures, with a primary focus on evaluating gap
260 junction dynamics. Using this approach, we established spheroids composed of the fibroblast line
261 CCD-112CoN (CRL-1541) and epithelial cell lines SW620, SW480, Caco-2, and HT-29, either
262 individually or in combination. The use of the 3D CellVivo culture system in combination with
263 Clinoreactor allowed for the controlled spheroid formation under low-shear microgravity
264 conditions. This environment minimizes mechanical stress while promoting cell aggregation and
265 tissue-like organization, resulting in spheroids with consistent size and morphology. Achieving a
266 target spheroid diameter of approximately 300 μ m ensures optimal conditions for microinjection,
267 as larger spheroids may pose increased risk of structural damage during manipulation, while

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268 smaller spheroids may lack the complexity required for physiologically relevant modeling.

269 Similarly, smaller spheroids will be difficult to separate from each other while larger spheroids
270 make separation of other spheroids easier.

271 Microinjection of Lucifer Yellow and Texas Red enables precise single-cell delivery
272 within the spheroid core, permitting visualization of dye diffusion through intercellular
273 pathways, including gap junctions. This approach provides a direct resolved method to study
274 cell-to-cell communication in a 3D context, overcoming limitations of conventional 2D assays
275 where cell morphology and extracellular matrix interactions differ significantly from in vivo
276 conditions. By controlling injection pressure, compensation pressure, and contact angle, the
277 method minimizes cell damage while ensuring reproducible dye loading.

278 Spheroids were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for one hour, ensuring adequate structural
279 preservation without excessive tissue hardening. Shorter times risk incomplete fixation and dye
280 loss, while longer times may reduce fluorescence intensity and increase autofluorescence,
281 making consistent fixation duration critical for reproducibility. However, fixation time might
282 have to be lessened or increased depending on downstream applications. Histological sectioning of
283 spheroids may require shorter fixation times to prevent excessive tissue hardening. This protocol
284 did not investigate whether the dye remains stable throughout the histology and sample
285 preparation process. All injections in this protocol were performed in glass-bottom 35 mm Petri
286 dishes, which facilitate visualization and maneuvering but also introduce fluid-flow that can
287 displace spheroids during approach. Embedding in thick extracellular matrices such as Matrigel
288 during injection was avoided, as the high viscosity can clog micropipette tips, dampen pressure
289 pulses, and necessitate higher injection pressures that may damage cells. If matrix support is
290 required, a thin surface coating may be preferred and alteration in pressure may be required.

291 Potential sources of technical error include excessive injection pressure, which can
292 rupture cells or disrupt spheroid integrity, and insufficient pressure, which may result in
293 inadequate dye delivery. Continuous dye leakage from the micropipette prior to entry can
294 produce high background fluorescence and lower the signal-to-noise ratio. Mechanical issues
295 such as micropipette tip breakage or passing entirely through the spheroid can lead to structural
296 damage and uneven dye distribution. Air bubbles within the pipette disrupt pressure control,
297 while spheroid drift in the Petri dish can cause missed entry points or shear damage. ECM-
298 related clogging is a particular challenge with viscous environments, and temperature
299 fluctuations can alter dye viscosity and membrane mechanics, affecting ejection consistency.
300 Mitigation strategies include filtering dyes through 0.22 μm membranes, using minimal and
301 incremental pressure adjustments, stabilizing spheroids against the chamber wall, keeping the
302 media depth moderate to reduce drift, and replacing pipettes at the first sign of clogging or
303 damage. Maintaining a bubble-free dye column, avoiding contact with the dish surface during
304 pipette insertion, and pre-testing injection stability before approaching the spheroid are also key
305 steps. Beyond the technical checklist, there are several elements that are difficult to capture in a
306 written protocol but critical to success. These include developing a feel for the subtle resistance
307 change when the micropipette pierces the spheroid, learning to adjust pressures dynamically
308 based on spheroid density and dye viscosity, and recognizing when a spheroid's position or
309 orientation will make injection more prone to damage.

310 The approach has inherent limitations. Microinjection is low throughput and requires specialized
311 equipment and operator training. Single-point injections may underestimate connectivity if the
312 spheroid contains necrotic zones or disconnected cell clusters. The method is also sensitive to
313 biological variables such as spheroid size and extracellular matrix composition. Overall, this

method offers a powerful tool for investigating cell-to-cell communication, permeability, and tissue organization in 3D models. It has potential applications in cancer biology, drug delivery studies, and developmental biology, where understanding how molecules move through tissue-like structures is critical.

Table 1:

<u>Issue</u>	<u>Potential Cause</u>	<u>Mitigation Strategy</u>
<u>Cell rupture / spheroid disruption</u>	<u>Excessive injection pressure</u>	<u>Apply minimal, incremental pressure adjustments: pre-test injection stability before approaching spheroid.</u>
<u>Inadequate dye delivery</u>	<u>Insufficient pressure; air bubble in pipette</u>	<u>Ensure bubble free dye column adjust pressure gradual back-fill carefully with micro loader.</u>
<u>High background fluorescence</u>	<u>Continuous dye leakage from pipette before entry</u>	<u>Keep needle tip out of medium until aligned, replace pipette if leakage occurs. use moderate pressure only after tip is inside cell. Wash spheroids at least 3 times with PBS</u>
<u>Structural damage / uneven dye spread</u>	<u>Micropipette tip breakage or passing entirely through spheroid</u>	<u>Avoid over-advancing needle. stop at cytoplasm of cells. replace pipette immediately if tip breaks.</u>
<u>Missed entry / shear damage</u>	<u>Spheroid drift in dish</u>	<u>Reduce medium depth stabilize spheroid against chamber wall or embed lightly in matrix cushion (last option)</u>
<u>Needle clogging</u>	<u>ECM components or viscous environments</u>	<u>Filter dyes through 0.22 µm membranes; replace pipette at first sign of clogging; avoid contact with dish surface.</u>
<u>Operator-dependent inconsistency</u>	<u>Difficulty detecting subtle resistance change when piercing spheroid</u>	<u>Practice to develop sensitivity; adjust pressures dynamically based on spheroid density and dye viscosity.</u>
<u>Biological variability</u>	<u>Necrotic zones, spheroid size</u>	<u>Standardize spheroid preparation (~200–400 µm), avoid injections into necrotic cores. use multiple spheroids per condition.</u>

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320 Authors contribution

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322 Conceptualization: Tomas Lugo, Thu Annelise Nguyen

323 Data curation: Tomas Lugo,

324 Formal analysis: Tomas Lugo, Thu Annelise Nguyen, Stephanie Myers

325 Funding acquisition: Thu Annelise Nguyen, Stephanie Myers

326 Investigation: Tomas Lugo,

327 Methodology: Tomas Lugo,

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332 Writing—original draft: Tomas Lugo

333 Writing—review and editing: Tomas Lugo, Thu Annelise Nguyen, Stephanie Myers

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340 Declaration of interests

341 *The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship,*

342 *and/or publication of this protocol.*

343 Data availability statement

344 *The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this ~~study~~ protocolk are*
345 *available within the article and its supplementary materials.*

346 Supplemental online material

347 Figures

348

349 *Figure 1: 40x Image of spheroid with micropipette needle and Caco-2 Spheroid*

350

351 *Figure 2: This figure presents an image of the FRTIC filter acquired at 20x magnification*
352 *following the injection procedure.*

353

354

355 *Figure 23: This figure displays a Caco-2 spheroid imaged after a 1-hour incubation period*
356 *before the washing step.*

357

358 *Figure 4: This figure showcases Microinjection system featuring the Eppendorf™*
359 *FemtoJet™ 4i Microinjector, TransferMan 4r Micromanipulator,*

360
361 *Figure 35: This figure represents Spheroids following 14 weeks of growth in the CelVivo*
362 *Clinostar system.*

363
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